

DNA barcoding of hoverflies (Diptera Syrphidae) – new species discovery in the *Merodon aureus* species group

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Abstract: *Merodon* is the richest genus of hoverflies in Europe with 120 recognized species. The adult species of this genus are important pollinators of diverse plants, while larvae are phytophagous and they develop in geophytes. Species discovery within genus is facilitated by the application of DNA barcoding approach in almost all recent studies. DNA barcoding is based on the analysis of sequence divergence of the short fragment on 5' end of mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I gene (COI), although, in hoverflies, both 5' and 3' COI sequences are equally used and often combined. The aim of this study was to identify hoverfly specimens collected in Morocco, Italy, Turkey and Georgia to a species level within the *M. aureus* species group. In order to achieve this, we analysed 5' COI sequences of aforementioned specimens. The sequences were blasted against the NCBI nucleotide database and used for Maximum parsimony and Maximum likelihood trees construction. Three new candidate species are discovered: *M. sp. nova* 1, *M. sp. nova* 2 and *M. aff. bessarabicus*. The three species are resolved as reciprocally monophyletic clades with strong branch support on both trees. In order to verify and describe the three species, additional examination of morphological character states is needed.

Keywords: COI gene; new species; molecular taxonomy

1. Introduction

The hoverfly genus *Merodon* Meigen, 1803 is known for its significant role in pollination, which makes it extremely important for research, in the age of pollinator population decline. It is the richest hoverfly genus in Europe, with 120 currently recognized species (Vujić *et al.* 2015) and approximately 160 described worldwide (Ståhls *et al.* 2009). It is distributed throughout the Palearctic and Afrotropical regions (Ståhls *et al.* 2009; Vujić *et al.* 2012). Larvae are phytophagous, while adult *Merodon* species feed on pollen and mimic bumblebees and bees (Hymenoptera: Apidae) (Speight, 2018). The genus was divided into five main lineages, (groups or clades) based on molecular analysis and adult morphology: *M. aureus*, *M. albifrons*, *M. desuturinus*, *M. natans* and *M. avidus-nigritarsis* lineage (Vujić *et al.* 2018). Each of these lineages comprises different species groups. According to Šašić *et al.* (2016) *M. aureus* species group contains 5 subgroups (*M. aureus*, *M. dobrogensis*, *M. cinereus*, *M. chalybeus* and *M. bessarabicus* subgroup). By definition, subgroups are established by morphological similarity and contain species complexes as well as species outside complexes. Species within complexes are morphologically inseparable or cryptic (Šašić *et al.* 2016). Hence, the presence of cryptic species and the lack of distinct diagnostic characters, makes the taxonomy of the *M. aureus* species group especially challenging and ever changing. Nonetheless, overcoming this problem has become easier with the

implementation and integration of various morphological, molecular and ecological tools. The integrative taxonomy approach has led to the description of many new taxa, previously unknown to science (Šašić *et al.* 2016, Šašić Zorić *et al.* 2018, 2020; Veselić *et al.* 2017; Radenković *et al.* 2018a.)

The development of integrative taxonomy is closely related to the emergence of DNA barcodes and the analysis of molecular markers for species identification and delineation. DNA barcoding in animals is based on the analysis of sequence divergence of the short fragment on the 5' end of mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I gene (COI) (Hebert *et al.* 2003a, b). However, in hoverflies, both 5' and 3' COI sequences are equally used and often combined (e.g. Šašić *et al.* 2016; Šašić Zorić *et al.* 2018; 2020; Radenković *et al.* 2018a).

This study aimed to generate DNA barcodes (5' COI gene sequences) and identify specimens collected in Morocco, Italy, Turkey and Georgia to a species level within the *M. aureus* species group.

2. Materials and Methods

Specimens of hoverflies were collected in Morocco, Italy, Turkey and Georgia (Table 1), and determined as members of the *Merodon aureus* species group by Ante Vujić.

Table 1. List of hoverfly specimens collected in Morocco, Italy, Turkey and Georgia.

DNA ID	5' COI haplotype	Species name	Country
AU449	Hap1	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Turkey
AU450	Hap1	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Turkey
AU452	Hap1	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Turkey
AU453	Hap1	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Turkey
AU454	Hap1	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Turkey
AU455	Hap1	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Turkey
AU457	Hap1	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Turkey
AU1497	Hap2	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1498	Hap3	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1499	Hap3	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1500	Hap4	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1501	Hap3	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1502	Hap3	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1503	Hap5	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1504	Hap3	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova1	Morocco
AU1507	Hap6	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova2	Italy
AU1509	Hap6	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova2	Italy
AU1511	Hap6	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova2	Italy
AU1513	Hap7	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova2	Italy
AU1516	Hap6	<i>Merodon</i> sp. nova2	Italy
AU1647	Hap8	<i>Merodon</i> aff. <i>bessarabicus</i>	Georgia ¹

¹ The specimen in the juvenile stage, pupa.

The genomic DNA was extracted from mid and hind legs of adult specimens, and the mid body part of the pupa following SDS (sodium-dodecyl-sulfate) DNA extraction protocol described in Chen *et al.* (2010). DNA vouchers are deposited at the Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology and Ecology, University of Novi Sad (FSUNS), Serbia.

The amplification of the 5' end of the COI gene was conducted using the LCO1490 and HCO2198 primer pair (Folmer *et al.* 1994). Polymerase chain reactions (PCR) were carried out in 25µl reaction volumes under the following conditions: 95°C for 2 min; 29 cycles of 94°C for 30 s each, 50°C for 30 s; 72°C for 2 min; with a final extension at 72°C for 8 min. The reaction mixture contained 1x reaction buffer (Thermo Scientific, Vilnius, Lithuania), 2.5mM MgCl₂, 0.1mM of each nucleotide, 1.25U Taq polymerase (Thermo Scientific, Vilnius, Lithuania), 5pmol of each primer, and approximately 50-100ng of template DNA. Amplifications were carried out using a Veriti 96 Well Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). The purification of PCR amplicons was conducted according to the manufacturer's instructions, using Exonuclease I and FastAP Thermosensitive Alkaline Phosphatase (Thermo Scientific, Vilnius, Lithuania). For each amplified fragment, sequencing was performed in a forward direction by the Sequencing Laboratory of the Finnish Institute for Molecular Medicine (Helsinki, Finland) and Macrogen Europe (Amsterdam, Netherlands).

The sequences were edited for base-calling errors using BioEdit 7.0.9.0. (Hall 1999) and aligned manually. The number of haplotypes was estimated using DNAsp v6.10.01 (Rozas *et al.* 2017). Haplotypes were compared with the sequence database of the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) using the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST, available at: <https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>, accessed 23 February 2017). Maximum Parsimony (MP) analysis was performed in NONA (Goloboff 1999) spawned with the aid of ASADO (Nixon 2008) using the heuristic search algorithm with 1,000 random addition replicates (mult*1,000), holding 100 trees per round (hold/100), maxtrees set to 100,000 and applying tree-bisection-reconnection (TBR) branch swapping. The bootstrap support values for clades were calculated with 1000 replicates. The Maximum Likelihood (ML) tree was constructed using RAxML 8.2.8 (Stamatakis 2014) using the CIPRES Science Gateway web portal (Miller *et al.* 2010) under the general time-reversible evolutionary model with a gamma distribution (GTRGAMMA) (Rodríguez *et al.* 1990). Nodal supports were estimated using rapid bootstrapping with 1000 replicates. The trees are rooted on *Eumerus amoenus* Loew, 1848, while the second outgroup was *M. luteofasciatus* Vujić, Radenković and Ståhls, 2018. Additionally, for each representative of the *M. aureus* species group, one sequence per species from Šašić Zorić (2018) was included in the analyses.

3. Results

The aligned sequences matrix of 5' COI gene is 593 bp long and does not contain gaps. We identified in total eight 5' COI gene haplotypes of 21 unidentified hoverfly specimens from Morocco, Italy, Turkey and Georgia (Table 1), four of which belong to Moroccan specimens, two to Italian specimens, one corresponds to Turkish specimens and one to the specimen from Georgia. The blast search of the NCBI nucleotide database using those haplotypes showed the highest nucleotide sequence similarity with species belonging to the *Merodon aureus* species group.

To identify analysed specimens to a species within the *M. aureus* species group we applied methods of phylogenetic tree construction. The analyses included 53 sequences

belonging to the *M. aureus* species group. Maximum parsimony (MP) analysis resulted in six equally parsimonious COI trees of 426 steps length (Ci=55 and Ri=86). The strict consensus tree is shown in Figure 1. Maximum likelihood (ML) analysis resulted in similar tree topology (Figure 2). Specimens from Morocco, Italy, Turkey and Georgia are placed in three separate and highly supported clades (bootstrap value: 100). The first clade comprises specimens from Morocco which are designated here as *M. sp. nova1*, while the second comprises specimens from Italy designated as *M. sp. nova2*. The third clade named *M. aff. bessarabicus* comprises specimens from Turkey which are morphologically inseparable from the species *M. bessarabicus* Paramonov, 1924 (A. Vujić, personal communication, 2020). The pupa from Georgia is a juvenile stage and based on its position on both trees probably belongs to *M. aff. bessarabicus*.

Figure 1. Strict consensus COI tree of six equally parsimonious trees for the *Merodon aureus* species group. Bootstrap values ≥ 50 are presented near nodes. Filled circles ● stand for unique changes, open circles ○ stand for non-unique changes.

Figure 2. Maximum likelihood COI tree of the *Merodon aureus* species group. Bootstrap values ≥ 50 are presented near nodes.

4. Discussion

During the last few decades molecular analyses became an important element of taxonomic studies helping to identify and delimit species, to conduct gender identification of the same species or to assign juvenile stages to a particular species (as it was predicted in Hebert *et al.* 2003a). Within the genus *Merodon* many new species are discovered thanks to the application of the COI gene.

In this study we discovered three new candidate species within the *Merodon aureus* species group based on analyses of the 5' COI gene sequences. All three species are resolved as reciprocally monophyletic clades with high bootstrap support values (100). Two of these, *M. sp. nova1* and *M. sp. nova2* have not been morphologically characterized, but the third, *M. aff. bessarabicus*, is morphologically very similar or cryptic to *M. bessarabicus* (A. Vujić, personal communication, 2020). Despite high morphological similarity, *M. aff. bessarabicus* is clearly genetically divergent from the latter species. Such high discordance between molecular and morphological divergence is unusual and can be either because cryptic species are differentiated by nonvisual mating signals and/or because of evolutionary mechanisms leading to morphological similarity comprising recent divergence, niche conservatism and morphological convergence (Bickford *et al.* 2006; Fišer *et al.* 2018). Thus, additional analyses of subtle changes in morphological characters, behavior, ecology and geography are important to resolve cryptic species (Goulding and Dayrat 2016; Padial *et al.* 2010).

The juvenile specimen from Georgia (AU1647) is related to specimens from Turkey. It is placed within the same clade with Turkish specimens and probably also belongs to *M. aff. bessarabicus*. However, additional specimens from Georgia and Turkey will be needed to confirm its species status.

The COI gene proved to be especially important for the discovery of cryptic species within *M. aureus* species group. Since the discovery of cryptic species within the *M. aureus* and *M. cinereus* complexes (Milankov *et al.* 2008), new species and species complexes within the group are recognized and described (the *M. atratus* species complex - Šašić *et al.*, 2016; the *M. luteomaculatus* species complex - Radenković *et al.* (2018b); the *M. caeruleascens* species complex - Šašić Zorić *et al.* 2018; the *M. dobrogensis* species subgroup – Šašić Zorić *et al.* 2020; the *M. aureus* species subgroup – Vujić *et al.* 2020). In all of these previous papers analyses of COI gene sequences were crucial.

5. Conclusions

In order to preserve existing diversity of pollinators and prevent further decline in their numbers it is important to accurately estimate their total diversity. In the search for appropriate methods to achieve this, a methodology based on molecular data has been introduced in taxonomy.

In this study we established the importance of molecular analysis in the discovery and delimitation of hoverfly species, and provided additional insight into the complex taxonomy of the *Merodon aureus* species group. The applied molecular marker, 5'COI gene, once again proved useful in the light of molecular taxonomy. However, in order to confirm the status of newly discovered species, the integrative taxonomic approach should be applied. Thus, it is recommended to combine the results of this study with the analyses of additional molecular markers, morphological data, morphometry, and ecological data.

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